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Understanding Demographic Dynamics

Agricultural Growth, Rural Poverty, and Sustainable Development

India's External Sector Reforms and Challenges

Exploring Tourism Opportunities and Overcoming Challenges in Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand

Climate Change and Environmental Degradation: A Global Challenge

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Impact of Traditional and Digital Financing Systems on Indian Exporters: A Comparative Study

Amrita Singh¹ & Dr Vivek Singh²

ABSTRACT

The financial system plays the main role in all export operations and growth. Financing is a key factor in the operation and expansion of exporters, specifically for developing economies like India. This evaluative study examines the impact of traditional and existing digital financing systems on Indian exporters and discusses their pros, cons, and latest developments. Indian exporters have historically relied on traditional aids, including bank loans, letters of credit (LCs), and trade credit. However traditional approaches are usually described as lengthy, and bulky, especially for Indian exporters who fail to qualify for the strict collateral and documentation provisions.

In India, however, access to financing for exporters is changing due to the impact of financial technology (FinTech). Quick, adaptive, and user-friendly products and services are available on digital platforms because of blockchain, P2P(Person-to-person) lending, and other online trade financing tools. These fintech technologies relieve bulky papers, increase the use of digital financial payment services, and extend the borrowing range for Indian exporters.

This research examines the two systems from numerous angles including but also provides data on risk, scalability, transaction speed, cost efficiency, and access. This research is based on secondary data. The data collected from government official websites and reports show the trends of Indian exports. The analysis indicates that the solution that is most likely to be effective in addressing the challenges of Indian exporters in the context of the digital economy would combine elements of both traditional and digital models of financing.

Keywords- *Digital Financing Systems, Traditional Banking Systems, Digital Payment Systems, FinTech.*

Introduction

India also owns one of the world's largest exporting industries including textile, drugs and pharma, IT & BPO, and agriculture. India's merchandise exports reached \$ 450 billion in FY 2022-

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2023 which is evidence of the increasing global role of India. Payment systems in this global trading context are specifically important since they guarantee payment regularity and export seller's receivables to accommodate the need for mutual trust between trading partners. For many years Indian exporters have continued to use traditional modes of payment like bank transfers, letters of credit, and demand drafts. Such systems are practically functional, including delays, high costs, and paperwork. With the initiation of new forms of digital payment platforms, the process of export payment has undergone a complete refit with swift, inexpensive, and efficient features. Other payments methods include National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT), Real Time Gross Settlement (RTGS), mobile wallets including the Unified Payment Interface (UPI), e-wallets like PayPal, fintech solutions including Payoneer, and blockchain solutions are emerging in the export fraternity. Digital India a campaign initiated by the Indian government has also pressured every sector towards reversions of this kind.

Review of Literature

Debesh Roy & Bijetri Roy (2022) highlight that India has set its target of reaching a US\$ 5 trillion GDP by 2025-26 to attain calls for 8-9% annual growth and will majorly rely on private investments and agriculture exports. The attainment of these goals can be realized through enhanced international trade, fair trade policies, and cutting-edge advances in technologies. ¹

A. K. Sen Gupta and P. K. Keshari (2013) explain that exports are essential for the development of the economy and the Indian financial system particularly the commercial banks avails pre-and post-shipment finance to the exporters. Nonetheless, some problems facing export credit consist of bank conservatism, interest rates, and coordination problems. ²

Shahana Mukherjee & Rupa Chanda (2021) studied by using a sample of 3,200 Indian manufacturing firms for the period 2000-2015, this paper investigates the export level effect of external financing constraints. That is why it discovers that increased financing constraints result in lower export levels, including SME businesses, and affiliation with a business group does not decrease this dependence. ³

Alam Ahmad & Prof. Abdul Aziz Ansari (2016) evaluate how EXIM Bank of India can support export trade financing to help Indian exporters and the role it plays throughout the business cycle. Even though EXIM Bank has different initiatives to increase export competitiveness and globalization of the rural industries. ⁴

Kati Suominen (2017) examines how disruptive technologies are changing global trade by providing smaller and bigger organizations with ways of doing cross-border trade more efficiently and effectively. Though the adoption of smart technologies is a critical success factor less developed countries, especially in Africa. ⁵

K. Rajamani & A.G. Rekha (2023) explained that COVID-19 has affected the MSMEs in all aspects of health and the economy, especially in the efficiency of financing. The study argues that it will be useful to improve ICT facilities, employ new models of lending, and the digitalization of payments to make the credit market more friendly for the development of MSMEs. ⁶

Sugandha Huria, Kriti Sharma, Neha Jain, & Ashley Jose (2022) explore the impact of digitalization in improving export intensity and export market entry of Indian manufacturing MSMEs using the data set 1990-2019. The given results show that a digitalization level is directly related to export intensity and market entry. ⁷

Mohit Sasan (2022) highlighted that the restrictions that came with the COVID-19 pandemic saw a decline of services exports by about 10% in the second quarter of 2020 because of financial and travel services mainly. But India has for the most part long-term advantages given that digital services constitute a reasonably stronger suit for India compared to a country like China. ⁸

Sivalingam Veeramani & Anam (2021) evaluated COVID-19 impact; travel, transport, and financial services bearing the major brunt. Nonetheless, the declines observed in India are not as steep as those in other major exporting countries, which implies that India has a strong prospect in mode (Digital Services) in the long run provided that it receives appropriate policy support immediately. ⁹

R. Pandimeenal (2024) explained that export finance involves the provision of credit to exporters to make exports less risky and to boost export trading. All the banks in Vellore actively participate in providing export credit significantly to the leather industry holding 37% of the export share of India. ¹⁰

Research Gap

Most of the existing research on traditional as well as digital financing systems affecting Indian exporters has been confined only to addressing the financial aspect or efficiency of trade-related processes. However, it is relevant that little comparative work has been done to link these two systems to the competitiveness and growth of exports by Indian exporters. Despite the growing interest in trade financing in the context of the digital transition, few prior works differentiate the difficulties in accessing both types of financing for exporters. This study is a targeted comparison, to understand the strengths and weaknesses of each system for Indian export.

Objectives of the study

1. To provide an overview of the comparison between traditional and digital financing impact on Indian exporters.
2. To evaluate the digital and traditional financial payment systems to identify the transaction speed, cost, security, and reliability for Indian exporters.
3. To analyze the governmental support for the better adoption of digital payment systems for Indian exporters.

Research Questions

1. How traditional and digital financing systems are different for Indian exporters?
2. Why do traditional and digital financial payments differ in speed, cost, security, and reliability for Indian exporters?

3. What is the governmental support for the better adoption of digital payment mechanisms for Indian exporters?

Methodology of research

This study aimed to analyze the impact of traditional and digital financing systems on Indian exporters and their impact on the speed, cost, security, and reliability of transactions. This present research employs only secondary data sources. Data and information have been collected from government publications such as the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), the Ministry of Commerce and Industry, and some other publications related to trade associations including the WTO database.

Overview of the comparison between traditional and digital financing impact on Indian Exporters.

Traditional Payment Methods

Traditional exchange payment systems have constituted the vital role of international trade for several decades. These methods include:

Bank Transfers (SWIFT, Wire Transfers): The most popular method of the traditional payment type is bank transfers, which work for foreign operations through the use of the SWIFT (Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunications) system. Although effective, this method may take several days and several intermediary financial institutions may be involved.

Letters of Credit (LCs): A letter of credit on the other hand is a financial document by a bank executed for and in favour of an importer but payable to the exporter provided certain terms and conditions are complied with such as production of shipping documents. At business risk and higher value dealings, LCs have been said to provide guarantees to the parties involved.

Demand Drafts and Checks: These are still used today but very rare in many sectors although low-value transactions they widely used. Demand drafts and checks take time because they are affected by post office and manual clearing.

Digital Payment Methods

The adoption of digital financial payments is gradually becoming a trend amongst many exporters, this has been made possible by the increase in technology and internet usage. Key digital payment methods include:

Online Banking (RTGS, NEFT, UPI): Indian domestic transactions employ both Real-Time Gross Settlement (RTGS) and National Electronic Funds Transfer (NEFT). The implantation of UPI in the banking system has made peer-to-peer transactions real-time and cost-friendly due to one-click money transfers. The use of UPI is gradually becoming popular in the export payment methods giving exporters an efficient and flexible method of receiving their payment.

E-Wallets and Payment Gateways (PayPal, Stripe, Razorpay): E-wallets enable exporters to receive payments from buyers in any part of the world, within a few seconds. PayPal and its

equivalent present secured procedures and simplicity in usage but are expensive due to high charges for cross-border transactions.

Fintech Platforms (Wise, Payoneer): Convenience, pecuniary specificity, and mediating functions, which are lower compared to traditional banks in terms of exchange rates, transaction fees, and time for settlements, are the functions of fintech solutions.

Blockchain and Cryptocurrencies: Through the usage of blockchain systems, cross-border payments can be processed instantly, charged relatively low fees, and added layers of security.

Table 1: Traditional vs. Digital financial Methods differ in transaction time and cost for Indian Exporters

Payment Method	Transaction Time	Transaction Cost
Bank Transfers (SWIFT)	3-7 days	3-6%
Letters of Credit (LCs)	7-14 days	4-8%
Demand Drafts/Checks	7-10 days	2-5%
NEFT/RTGS/UPI	1-2 days	0.5-2%
PayPal/Stripe/Razorpay	1 day (instant)	2-5%
Blockchain Payments	Near-instant	Minimal

Figure 1: Traditional vs. Digital financial Methods differ in transaction time and cost for Indian Exporters

Source: RBI and Ministry of Commerce and Industry

Table 2: Traditional and digital financial methods differ in adoption rate, security and also getting government support

Payment Method	Adoption Rate	Security	Government Support
Bank Transfers (SWIFT)	75%	High	Moderate
Letters of Credit (LCs)	60%	Very High	Low
Demand Drafts/Checks	10%	Moderate	Low
NEFT/RTGS/UPI	50%	High	High
PayPal/Stripe/Razorpay	30%	High	Moderate
Blockchain Payments	<10%	Very High	Low

Figure 2: Traditional and digital financial methods differ in adoption rate, security and also getting government support

Source: RBI and ministry of Commerce and Industry

Interpretation and Analysis of the impact of traditional and digital financing systems on Indian Exporters

Transaction Speed: Another key difference between traditional and digital payment systems technology is the speed of the transactions. The data shows that bank transfers can take 3 to 7 days, while letters of credit may take 7 to 14 days to be completed. On the other hand, the use of digital payments from near-instantaneous or same-day facilities significantly enhances exporters' liquidity.

The NEFT, RTGS, and UPI allow payment transfers to be made between 1-2 days while sort payment processing like PayPal, Payoneer, and the like offers instant payment though, they are costly. Unified Payments Interface for the international transaction part of India's FI movement has markedly reduced the time for payments.

Transaction Costs: The commonly used payment methods are relatively costly for Indian exporters. The general SWIFT transfer charge falls within the range of \$300 to \$ 600 and the average transaction cost is between 3%-6% of the total transaction value. Although letters of credit offer a great measure of assurance, they may be somewhat expensive because they require volumes of paperwork and bank guarantees; approximately 4% -8%.

This kind of payment processing system does not cost as much and sometimes costs even less, per transaction in comparison to a traditional payment method. For domestic transactions, popular NEFT and RTGS payment methods feature minimal rates of 0.5-2%, which is suitable for exporters. However, using sites like PayPal is convenient, but these sites entail higher charges against international transactions, which cost between 2%-5%.

Security: Exporters are very sensitive to the issue of security especially when dealing with large-value companies. This is because letters of credit together with other traditional techniques of payment are regarded as highly safe. Bank transfers are also safe and that is especially the case when using the SWIFT network. Demand drafts and checks, thus are less secure as these can be forged. Still, Digital payments are faster and can be cheaper as a rule, but they are vulnerable to cyber threats and fraud. Business owners sending and receiving money through PayPal, Payoneer, or similar service providers must make sure their accounts have encryption.

Financial Assistance granted by the government and approval or rejection by government agencies

Digital adoption by consumers in India has been driven primarily by the Indian government through the Digital India initiative. This was launched in 2015 and its goal is to try and make as many people and businesses as possible financially included by being willing to adopt digital payments. Payments through UPI, more specifically for the intra-country payments have transformed the payment system in India and now attempts are being made to take it to the cross-border trade payments as well. RBI has also issued guidelines to support a change from conventional to electronic payments for exporters.

Impact of Payment Systems on Indian Exporters

General Improvement of Efficiency and Cash Flows: The movement to digital forms of payments for exports has impacted the productivity of exporters provided they have appropriate access to efficient cash flows. Digital payments enable exporters to access the funds much faster than it would take under traditional systems. On the other hand, the time consumed in using the traditional forms of payment has a way of slowing down cash flow.

Enhanced Competitiveness: It also has the potential to offer flexible, faster payment modes as a strategic weapon for Indian exporters. The expectation of export partners that they have to meet to

develop long-term business associations with global buyers. Through cheap and fast transaction charges, Players such as Payoneer give Indian exporters a competitive edge, especially in price-related markets like India. Furthermore, the Government of India's drive towards encouraging digital transactions alongside the emergence of India as a digital economy also greatly enhances the competitiveness of exporters in India.

Security and Risk Management: the threats associated with the use of digital payments as a method of payment are still a pain point for exporters since security always remains a key concern no matter how efficient a payment method is. Soon digital platforms employ better encryption and fraud monitoring systems but they stay open to cyber incidents. Reducing the possibility of fraud and change is made possible by the use of an open and fixed ledger known to all by the use of blockchain.

Conclusion

This comparative study highlights the growing importance of digital payment systems in India's export sector. While traditional payment methods such as bank transfers and letters of credit remain important for high-value and high-risk transactions, digital platforms offer numerous advantages in terms of speed, cost, and efficiency.

The Indian government has played a critical role in facilitating this transition through initiatives like Digital India and the promotion of UPI for international payments. However, challenges remain, particularly in terms of security and regulatory clarity, especially concerning blockchain and cryptocurrency payments.

The continued adoption of digital financial payment systems will be crucial for the future growth of India's export sector. By embracing these technologies and addressing the associated risks, Indian exporters can enhance their global presence and improve their operational efficiency. As the digital payment ecosystem evolves, Indian exporters are well-positioned to capitalize on the opportunities presented by this transformation.

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